

Interaction of Aliphatic Amines, Ammonia and Alkali with 5-Alkyl or Aryl Amino-substituted-3-imino-1,2,4-dithiazolidines (Thiurets): Formation of Related Cyanothiocarbamide Salts

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The aromatic amines by their interaction with 5-substituted amino-3-imino-1,2,4-dithiazolidines have been reported to form the related *N*-arylformamidino-*N'*-substituted thiocarbamides. In contrast to this, aliphatic amines are now found to afford only the corresponding salts of the related cyanothiocarbamides.

The interaction of 5-alkyl-or-arylamino-substituted-3-imino-1,2,4-dithiazolidines with aromatic amines has been shown to afford the related *N*-arylformamidino-*N'*-alkyl-or-arylthiocarbamides¹ (I)

(where R=Ph, *p*-Tol, *p*-phenetyl or Me, Et, Me₂, etc.).

The reaction has now been studied with respect to methylamine, ammonia, and alkali with 5-methyl-, 5-dimethyl-, 5-ethyl-, 5-phenyl-, and 5-*p*-tolyl-amino-substituted derivatives of 3-imino-1,2,4-dithiazolidines.

With aqueous solutions of ammonia and methylamine, the above 5-methylamino- and 5-dimethylamino-dithiazolidines form the ammonium and methylammonium salts (II) respectively of the related *N*-methyl- and *N*-dimethyl-*N'*-cyanothiocarbamides. These are isomeric with the related guanidine derivatives of the type (I), but from their general behaviour and chemical properties there is no doubt about their salt-like character. The above reactions can be represented as:

(where R' is a Me or H).

*The negative charge on the anion of this salt can be shared between S and the atoms of the triad NCN individually or jointly.

1. This *Journal*, 1960, **37**, 151; 1961, **38**, 221; *Proc. Ind. Sci. Cong.*, 1961, Part III, p.102.

When the aqueous solutions of (II) are treated with acid, free cyanothiocarbamides (IV) are precipitated, identity of which has been proved by comparison with the cyanothiocarbamides and their alkyl derivatives obtained directly from the appropriate alkyl isothiocyanates and disodium cyanamide². Compound (IV) on treatment with alkali or ammonia affords the related salts (II).

Compound (III) on treatment with alkali gave among other products two compounds of probable structures (V) and (VI). But since the same compounds are also obtained (vide Experimental) by the condensation of methyl isothiocyanate and disodium cyanamide, the decomposition of compound (III) can be tentatively formulated as:

On reaction of these dithiazolidines with alkali, sodium salts of the corresponding cyanothiocarbamides are formed in solution, as indeed had been observed earlier by Hantzsch and Wolverkamp³ in the case of 5-phenylamino-3-imino-1,2,4-dithiazolidine. On acidification, the free cyanothiocarbamides are precipitated which, when aryl-substituted, change rapidly into complicated products; on direct alkylation of the alkaline solutions, related *S*-alkyl-*N*-cyanoisothiocarbamides are formed as expected.

5-Phenylamino- and 5-*p*-tolylamino-3-imino-1,2,4-dithiazolidines on reaction with aqueous or ethanolic ammonia formed the expected ammonium salts of the related cyanothiocarbamides. But since the free cyanothiocarbamides were very unstable and rapidly underwent complex changes, including perhaps polymerisation, in these cases, their ammonium salts of sufficient analytical purity could not be obtained. But their identity was established by benzylating the rather crude products when *S*-benzyl-*N*-phenyl- and *S*-benzyl-*N*-*p*-tolyl-*N'*-cyanoisothiocarbamides were obtained.

2. Wunderlich, *Ber.*, 1886, 19, 449, 451; Hecht, *Ber.*, 1890, 23, 1658; 1892, 25, 762.

3. *Annalen*, 1904, 331, 277, 296.

EXPERIMENTAL

Action of Methylamine and Ammonia on 5-Methylamino- and 5-Dimethylamino-3-imino-1,2,4-dithiazolidine Hydroiodides: Formation of the Related Salts of the Respective Cyanthiocarbamides

(a). *Methylamine Salt of N-Methyl-N'-cyanthiocarbamide*.—5-Methylamino-3-imino-1,2,4-dithiazolidine hydroiodide (5 g.) was heated under reflux for 15 minutes with a 33% aqueous solution of methylamine (5 ml) and ethanol (25 ml). The reaction mixture was cooled and the separated sulphur filtered. The clear filtrate on concentration and cooling deposited crystals (1.5 g.). It was crystallised from ethanol, m. p. 135°. (Found: C, 31.98; H, 6.55; N, 38.29; S, 21.91. $C_4H_{10}N_4S$ requires C, 32.87; H, 6.84; N, 38.35; S, 22.32%.)

(b). *Ammonium Salt of N-Methyl-N'-cyanthiocarbamide*.—5-Methylamino-3-imino-1,2,4-dithiazolidine hydroiodide, when treated as above with strong ethanolic or aqueous ammonia, afforded a product in good yield, m. p. 145-46°. It was crystallised from ethanol, m. p. 147°. (Found: C, 27.39; H, 5.96; N, 42.23; S, 23.83. $C_3H_8N_4S$ requires C, 27.27; H, 6.06; N, 42.42; S, 24.24%). The corresponding isomeric *N*-methyl-*N'*-formamidinothiocarbamide was obtained by condensation of methyl isothiocyanate and guanidine carbonate¹ and found to be different from this substance.

(c). *Methylamine Salt of NN-Dimethyl-N'-cyanthiocarbamide*.—5-Dimethylamino-3-imino-1,2,4-dithiazolidine hydroiodide, when treated with aqueous or ethanolic methylamine, as described under (a), afforded a product which was crystallised from absolute ethanol, m. p. 118°. (Found: C, 37.68; H, 7.65; N, 34.72; S, 20.14. $C_5H_{12}N_4S$ requires C, 37.50; H, 7.50; N, 35.0; S, 20.0%.)

(d). *Ammonium Salt of NN-Dimethyl-N'-cyanthiocarbamide*.—5-Dimethylamino-3-imino-1,2,4-dithiazolidine hydroiodide, when treated with ammonia as described above, afforded the ammonium salt of the related cyanthiocarbamide. It was crystallised from ethanol, m. p. 161°. (Found: C, 33.15; H, 6.66; N, 38.14; S, 22.19. $C_4H_{10}N_4S$ requires C, 32.87; H, 6.84; N, 38.35; S, 21.97%.)

The compounds described under (a), (b), (c), and (d) are very soluble in water and liberate ammonia or the amine when treated with cold alkali.

Preparation of Free Cyanthiocarbamides from the above Salts and their Characterisation

(a). The aqueous solutions of the methylammonium and ammonium salts of *N*-methyl-*N'*-cyanthiocarbamide, described above, when acidified, precipitated the identical free *N*-methyl-*N'*-cyanthiocarbamide. The product was crystallised from ethanol, m. p. 118° (decomp.). (Found: C, 31.62; H, 4.15; N, 36.59; S, 27.91. $C_3H_7N_3S$ requires C, 31.30; H, 4.34; N, 36.52; S, 27.82%). This was found identical with the authentic sample prepared from methyl isothiocyanate and disodium cyanamide², m. p. 118°. (Found: N, 36.81; S, 27.98. $C_3H_7N_3S$ requires N, 36.52; S, 27.82%). It gave an *S*-methyl derivative by its methylation with methyl iodide in ethanolic solution. It was crystallised from ethanol,

1. Kurzer, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 2292.

m.p. 196°. The methyl derivative did not show any depression in melting point when mixed with the *S*-methyl derivative obtained from the above described authentic sample of *N*-methyl-*N'*-cyanothiocarbamide² during the preparation of which it was observed that when the solution containing methyl isothiocyanate and disodium cyanamide was acidified, instead of the expected cyanothiocarbamide an explosive compound precipitated. On filtration of this and rebasification of the filtrate, another product, m.p. 287-89°, was obtained. Both the products were also obtained when *N*-methyl-*N'*-cyanoformamidine disulphide, the oxidation product of methylcyanothiocarbamide, was decomposed with alkali (*vide infra*).

(b). Similarly, when the well-cooled aqueous solutions of the methylammonium and the ammonium salts of *N*-dimethyl-*N'*-cyanothiocarbamide were treated with dilute hydrochloric acid, the free *N*-dimethyl-*N'*-cyanothiocarbamide, m.p. 77°, was precipitated (*vide infra*).

Oxidation of the Methylammonium and Ammonium Salts of N-Methyl- and N-Dimethyl-N'-cyanothiocarbamides: Formation of N-Methyl- and N-Dimethyl-N'-cyanoformamidine Disulphides

(a). The methylammonium salt of *N*-methyl-*N'*-cyanothiocarbamide (2 g.) was dissolved in ethanol (10 ml) containing a few drops of HCl (conc.). Hydrogen peroxide was added dropwise with stirring when a microcrystalline powder gradually separated. This was filtered (0.75 g.); m.p. 149° (decomp.). (Found: C, 31.68; H, 3.48; N, 36.42; S, 28.18. $C_6H_9N_6S_2$ requires C, 31.57; H, 3.50; N, 36.84; S, 28.07%).

(b). The ammonium salt of *N*-methyl-*N'*-cyanothiocarbamide also on oxidation as above afforded the same product, m.p. 151° (decomp.). It showed no depression in melting point when mixed with the oxidation product obtained above. (Found: C, 31.93; H, 3.74; N, 36.49; S, 28.28. $C_6H_9N_6S_2$ requires C, 31.57; H, 3.50; N, 36.84; S, 28.07%).

(c). To an ice-cold aqueous solution (10 ml) of methylammonium salt of *N*-dimethyl-*N'*-cyanothiocarbamide (2 g.) a dilute aqueous solution of iodine in potassium iodide was added gradually with constant stirring, crystals separated, m.p. 118-20°. On rapid crystallisation from ethanol m.p. rose to 121°. (Found: N, 33.12. $C_8H_{12}N_6S_2$ requires N, 32.81%).

(d). The ammonium salt of *N*-dimethyl-*N'*-cyanothiocarbamide was oxidised in a similar manner with iodine when the above described product, m.p. 121°, was obtained; it gave no depression in melting point when mixed with it. (Found: C, 37.73; H, 5.0; N, 32.47; S, 25.20. $C_8H_{12}N_6S_2$ requires C, 37.50; H, 4.68; N, 32.81; S, 25.0%).

Decomposition of N-Methyl-N'-cyanoformamidine Disulphide by Alkali

The *N*-methyl-*N'*-cyanoformamidine disulphide was treated with an excess of cold aqueous alkali for 30 minutes. The separated sulphur was filtered and the filtrate examined as follows:

(i). A part was acidified when a product separated which did not show a sharp m.p. and could not be identified. The clear filtrate from this on rebasification precipitated another substance which was crystallisable from absolute ethanol, m.p. 289-91°. [Found:

C, 29.73; H, 4.66; N, 43.60; S, 19.83. $C_6H_7N_3S$ (corresponding to $MeNHC-NH-C:NH$ the condensation product of $CH_3NHCSNHCN$ and NH_2CN) requires $\begin{array}{c} \parallel \\ S \end{array} \begin{array}{c} | \\ NHCN \end{array}$
 C, 30.57; H, 4.45; N, 44.58; S, 20.37%].

(ii). Another part of the alkaline filtrate was acidified and filtered. To the filtrate dilute hydrogen peroxide was added when the original *N*-methyl-*N'*-cyanoformamidine disulphide was precipitated, m.p. (147-49°) indicating that *N*-methyl-*N'*-cyanthiocarbamide was one of the products of alkali decomposition of its disulphide oxidation product⁵.

Action of Alkali on 5-Methyl-, 5-Dimethyl-, and 5-Ethyl-amino-3-imino-1,2,4-dithiazolidines

(a). The 5-methylamino-3-imino-1,2,4-dithiazolidine (10 g.) was treated with an excess of cold alkali for 30 minutes. Separated sulphur was filtered, the filtrate made just acidic with HCl, and the precipitated product was again filtered. The clear filtrate was examined as follows:

(i) A part was basified and heated on a water bath under reflux with methyl iodide (3.5 g.) and ethanol (15 ml). On cooling, crystals of *S*-methyl-*N*-methyl-*N'*-cyanoisothiocarbamide separated, m.p. 196° (*vide supra*).

(ii) To another part of the filtrate was added HCl (conc., 2 ml). On keeping, as expected, *N*-methyl-*N'*-cyanthiocarbamide (m.p. 118°) separated. In some experiments, however, another substance of an explosive nature separated, m.p. 135-45° (decomp.). [Found: C, 36.75; H, 4.24; N, 42.52; S, 18.14. $C_6H_8N_6S$ (the sum of the composition of methyleyanthiocarbamide and methyleyanocarbodiimide corresponding to $MeNHC-N:C:NC-NHCN$) requires C, 36.73; H, 4.08; N, 42.80; S, 16.32%].

After separation of this compound the clear filtrate on basification gave another product, m.p. 289-91°. This showed no depression in m.p. when mixed with the product obtained from the decomposition of *N*-methyl-*N'*-cyanoformamidine disulphide (*vide supra*).

(iii) The product, precipitated on acidification of the original reaction mixture, was found to be a hydroiodide, m.p. 261°. (Found: N, 14.97; S, 23.47. $C_5H_5N_3S_2 \cdot HI$ requires N, 15.27; S, 23.27%). It appeared to be an isomorphous form of 5-methylamino-3-imino-1,2,4-dithiazolidine hydroiodide, reported to melt at 204°.

(b). 5-Dimethylamino-3-imino-1,2,4-dithiazolidine (5 g.) was treated with an excess of dilute aqueous alkali at room temperature for 30 minutes. The separated sulphur was filtered and the filtrate acidified with HCl (conc.) when a product precipitated which was crystallised from absolute ethanol, m.p. 77°. (Found: N, 32.28; S, 25.0. $C_6H_7N_3S$ requires N, 32.55; S, 24.80%). The identity of this substance with *N*-dimethyl-*N'*-cyanthiocarbamide was established by its condensation with aniline and *p*-phenetidine when the respective *N*-arylfornamido-*N'*-dimethylthiocarbamides were obtained which could be oxidised to the corresponding 3-arylamino-5-dimethylamino-1,2,4-thiadiazoles⁶.

5. Cf. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, 101, 2166, 2180.

6. *This Journal*, 1961, 38, 221.

The above *N*-dimethyl-*N'*-cyanothiocarbamide on treatment with ammonia and methylamine formed the corresponding salts, m.p. 161° and 118°, which gave no depression in m.p. when mixed with the products obtained by direct reaction of ammonia and methylamine on dithiazolidine (*vide supra*). Both gave the same oxidation product, m.p. 121°, which showed no depression when mixed with the oxidation product described above.

(c). 5-Ethylamino-3-imino-1,2,4-dithiazolidine (5 g.) was treated with cold aqueous alkali for 30 minutes. The separated sulphur was filtered; from the filtrate on acidification and cooling a product separated, m.p. 55-56°. On keeping it decomposed to a pasty mass which hardened afterwards. (Found: N, 32.14. $C_4H_7N_3S$ requires N, 32.55%). The product was dissolved in EtOH-NaOH and methylated with methyl iodide as usual. On cooling, the crystals of *S*-methyl-*N*-ethyl-*N'*-cyanoisothiocarbamide separated, which were recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 162°. The same *S*-methyl derivative was also obtained by methylation of *N*-ethyl-*N'*-cyanothiocarbamide, obtained from ethyl isothiocyanate and disodium cyanamide²; m.p. 162°. The products showed no depression in m.p. when mixed.

Interaction of 5-Phenylamino- and 5-p-Tolylamino-3-imino-1,2,4-dithiazolidine Hydrochlorides with Ammonia

(a). The 5-phenylamino-3-imino-1,2,4-dithiazolidine salts on treatment with ammonia and working up as in the above cases gave a crude ammonium salt which could not be purified by crystallisation. The free phenylcyanothiocarbamide could not be isolated. The crude ammonium salt on direct benzoylation with benzyl chloride in ethanolic medium afforded the *S*-benzyl-*N*-phenyl-*N'*-cyanoisothiocarbamide, m.p. 186°. Fromm *et al.*³ recorded m.p. 186°. (Found: N, 15.65. Calc. for $C_{13}H_{13}N_3S$: N, 15.73%).

(b). The 5-*p*-tolylamino-3-imino-1,2,4-dithiazolidine behaved similarly with ammonia and the formation of the ammonium salt of *N*-*p*-tolyl-*N'*-cyanothiocarbamide was inferred from the formation of the related *S*-benzyl derivative from the crude ammonium salt; crystals from ethanol, m. p. 181°. (Found: N, 14.79. $C_{16}H_{15}N_3S$ requires N, 14.94%).

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